

DEVELOPING WRITING SKILLS IN ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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The developing of the language skills has always been a very hard and an interesting task. The process of writing suggests that we can actually teach students how to write with coherence, an appropriate grammar structure and an acceptable spelling. One of the effective ways to do this is to motivate the students and make them aware of the steps involved in effective writing. Four reasons why students dislike writing are: It leaves as more permanent record of proficiency than speaking; so it seems a threat for them. Students feel that they lack sufficient knowledge of the language. Students believe that writing must be grammatically correct. They think that formal correctness must be achieved at their very first attempt. The seven effective writing strategies are: 1) Pre-writing 2) early composing 3) planning and organizing 4) later composing 5) final composing 6) revising 7) editing. When we talk about writing is necessary to remember that there are three inseparable aspects when teaching it; Writing as a channel of a foreign language is the use of it alongside listening, speaking and reading in the process of learning important elements of the language; Writing as a goal of a foreign language learning, is the development of writing skills to fill such purposes as: note-taking, summarizing, narrating, reporting for various real-life situations and Writing with cohesion, is the employment of various linguistic means by which the parts of a written text are related to one another, with continuity and organization. In our times, there is an increasing tendency of showing communication rather than the mere practice of linguistic forms. But we have to be careful because texts are made of sentences putting together for communicative purposes. The writing activities should be geared to their needs and interests. They should be linked to the real life whenever possible. From our point of view, a practical teaching idea has something to do with a good idea, characterized by being attractive, exciting to real life and taking into account the environment, context and most of all, the learners' needs and interests. Thus, teachers should know how to teach writing to be effective. As it is known, writing is considered a very complex task for teachers and mainly for students. The heart of the language lessons is the communicative activity itself, so modern courses of English. On the other hand, students should learn grammar rules, hear

and read authentic English as much as they can, look at the vocabulary notes everyday and other necessary activities to develop the writing skills. Teachers should be facilitators and are responsible of creating the best possible conditions for learning. So, we will list some useful and practical teaching ideas for the developing of the writing skills: It is very important to teach pronunciation in English of the different signs of punctuations (E.g. coma, period, brackets, quotations, semi colon, etc) in order to identify them when taking dictation. Writing of sentences paragraphs, compositions. Provide Problem solving tasks. For instance: Give a suitable end to this story. If you were in this situation what would you do, write it. Writing of authentic texts linked to real life situations such as: notes, telegrams, postcards, letters, commercials, summaries for research works. Linguistic games such as: Crosswords, Word Association, Guessing the word. Checking dictation by means of interchanging the student's notebooks, giving a correct model on board as a guide for corrections. Exercises of different types using connectors, the use of them are indispensable for a right coherence. Reading a given text 2 or 3 times and then students have to remember as much as they can to write it (it could be developed in teams) Give the winner. Developing writing competitions on board: words, sentences. In free writing students will write about free topics. Such as culture, history, sports, etc. Filling cards or charts like this:

Letter	Name of job	Action (verb)	Country
A	Assistant	associate	Angola
B	builder	build	Bolivia

They could be modified using other kind of categories. A practical teaching idea may be the solution to avoid "boring lessons" in the English learning process. Theory and Practice must always be together to get good results in learning any foreign language, as well as, making a right use of a variety of methodological approaches.

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